

Kurianova Irina Vladimirovna,

Ph.D. in Economics,

Associate Professor of the Department of Finance and Credit,

Institute of Economics and Management,

V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University, Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Kravchenko Larisa Anatolyevna,

Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor,

Associate Professor of the Department of Enterprise Economics,

Institute of Economics and Management,

V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,

Simferopol, Russian Federation.

Gindes Elena Grigorievna,

PhD in Public Administration, Associate Professor,

Professor of the Department of Advertising, Public Relations and Publishing,

Institute of Media Communications, Media Technologies and Design,

V.I. Vernadsky Crimean Federal University,

Simferopol, Russian Federation.

**FUNCTIONING AND MODERNIZATION OF THE FINANCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE
OF RUSSIA IN THE ERA OF GEOECONOMIC CHANGES**

The article examines the functioning and modernization of the financial infrastructure of the Russian Federation under new geoeconomic challenges. It is established that financial infrastructure possesses the characteristics of a public good, which renders market mechanisms insufficient for its development. The study analyzes investment barriers associated with the high capital intensity and long payback periods of infrastructure projects, as well as risks arising from underinvestment in technological sovereignty and cybersecurity. To quantitatively assess the level of development and resilience of the financial infrastructure—and to identify systemic vulnerabilities impeding Russia’s financial sovereignty and technological independence in the face of geoeconomic pressures—the following key indicators are considered: the share of domestic software in the banking sector; availability of a national operating system for critical infrastructure; deployment of domestic database management systems in financial institutions; level of automation in responding to cyber incidents; integration of artificial intelligence into threat detection systems; volume of state investment in cybersecurity (as a percentage of GDP). Special attention is given to the State System for Detection, Prevention, and Mitigation of Computer Attacks, a central element of Russia’s national cybersecurity architecture, which plays a crucial role in ensuring the stability of the financial infrastructure. The paper emphasizes that overcoming these systemic constraints requires a comprehensive concept of technological sovereignty in financial infrastructure, built upon three interrelated components: institutional, investment-related, and technological. A performance evaluation framework is proposed, based on six key dimensions aligned with the structure of this concept. It is substantiated that ensuring the resilience and independence of financial infrastructure necessitates deliberate state regulation and a strategic shift from reactive adaptation to a proactive, anticipatory development approach.

Keywords: financial infrastructure, public good, investment barriers, cybersecurity, technological sovereignty, government regulation.

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